

ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN BUSINESS ACROSS SECONDARY, TERTIARY, AND QUATERNARY SECTORS

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Abstract

Within the Romanian economic landscape, a shift is observed as the primary and secondary sectors experience a decline in value, countered by substantial growth in the tertiary and quaternary sectors, particularly within the services domain. This paper centers its hypotheses on leveraging the potential of Romanian mountainous regions for the advancement of specific sectors. A strategic blend of secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors with agriculture emerges as a focal point. The emphasis lies on catalyzing Information and Communication Technology (ICT) development, fostering the clustering of evolved and emerging industries such as textiles and wood, and intensifying food processing and agro-food production. The integration

of these elements aims to spur holistic development, with a keen focus on the unique opportunities offered by Romania's mountainous terrain.

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Keywords: mountain entrepreneurship, mountain theoretical approach, mountain science

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Introduction:

Romania's mountainous regions, adorned with natural beauty, have become more than just picturesque landscapes. They serve as the backdrop for a burgeoning business environment that spans the secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors. This article embarks on an exploration of how entrepreneurial endeavors in these sectors have evolved against the breathtaking backdrop of Romanian mountains. (Covaci B & Covaci M, 2021a-h; Covaci M & Covaci B, 2021a-h)

The Ascendance of Mountain Entrepreneurship:

In recent years, Romania has witnessed a notable surge in economic activities nestled within its mountainous terrains. The secondary sector, encompassing industries and manufacturing, has seen a steady rise.

PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW JOURNAL (2/2021)

Simultaneously, the tertiary sector, focused on services, and the quaternary sector, involving knowledge-based activities, have experienced significant growth.

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Challenges and Opportunities:

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While the ascent in mountain entrepreneurship is evident, it is essential to acknowledge the challenges and opportunities inherent in this unique business landscape. The idyllic setting presents an enticing canvas, but it also poses challenges, especially for the primary sector, which sometimes takes a backseat in the pursuit of progress.

Ensuring sustainable and quality food production becomes a critical concern, demanding careful consideration from public governance. The delicate balance between economic development and environmental preservation requires strategic solutions that foster collaboration across sectors.

Sectors Under the Lens:

This article scrutinizes various sectors within Romania's mountain business environment, providing insights into their dynamics:

PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW JOURNAL (2/2021)

- Industry, Construction, and Services (Ix): An amalgamation of diverse activities forming the backbone of mountain entrepreneurship.

6

- Wholesale and Retail Trade; Repair of Motor Vehicles and Motorcycles (Ix1): Examining the commerce and repair activities that contribute to the economic tapestry.

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- Professional, Scientific, and Technical Activities; Administrative and Support Activities (Ix2): Delving into the knowledge-based services that thrive in mountainous regions.

- Transport and Storage (Ix5): Unveiling the logistics and transportation intricacies crucial for connectivity in mountainous terrain.

- Accommodation and Food Services (Ix7): Exploring the hospitality and culinary ventures that capitalize on the region's allure.

- Information and Communication (Ix8): Analyzing the role of technology and communication in fostering mountain business.

- Education, Human Health, and Social Assistance (Ix9): Understanding the contributions of educational and healthcare services to mountain communities.

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- Financial and Insurance Activities; Real Estate Activities (Ix10): Investigating the financial and real estate dimensions shaping the mountain business landscape.

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Results:

The ascent of mountain entrepreneurship finds support in significant investments dedicated to the development of mountainous areas and initiatives aimed at repopulating these regions. Within the European Union, mountainous terrains are recognized for their immense potential in organic farming and contributions to human health. The air-water-soil ecosystem in these areas is perceived as less polluted compared to other topographical landscapes. The legislative framework specific to mountain areas, a unique feature within Europe, reflects the importance Europeans attribute to sustainable mountain science as a driver of economic development.

The conviction in the potential of mountain entrepreneurship, particularly in terms of employability, is a recurring theme in studies and applications,

PSYCHO-SOCIAL VIEW JOURNAL (2/2021)

drawing the attention of both public and corporate governance in European countries.

8

The author asserts that the agri-food industry is pivotal for Romania's future, aligning with studies predicting an unprecedented agri-food crisis (Zaman et al., 2013; Benaki et al., 2007). This paper offers solutions tailored to Romania's dynamics, utilizing Eurostat indices on business demography for a comprehensive analysis.

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Employing the Eurostat classification, the paper conducts an in-depth examination of industry, services, and the quaternary sector within the broader sector of Industry, Construction, and Services, excluding insurance activities (encompassing secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors). The results, processed using SPSS, are derived from the authors' calculations based on Eurostat data, as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Active enterprises in the mountainous area of Romania - Secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors (except agriculture)

Source: Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

For the computation, the researchers utilized eight variables spanning the years 2008-2018, with SPSS recognizing and validating all data points (no data invalidations were recorded). The constituent sub-sectors witnessed substantial growth during the examined period (2008-2018), showcasing increases as follows: Ix1 by 132.95%, Ix2 by 182.56%, Ix3 by 134.26%, Ix4 by 134.13%, Ix5 by 220.71%, Ix6 by 441.63%, Ix7 by 180.84%, Ix8 by 226.81%, Ix9 by 326.02%, and Ix10 by 183.50% (refer to Figure 2).

Figure 2. The variation in the period 2008 - 2018 of the constituent sub-sectors for secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors

Source: Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

The observed elevation signifies a continuous upward trajectory in the mountainous business environment across Romania's secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors, occasionally at the expense of the primary sector. As ensuring food provision, especially of high quality, remains a paramount global and national concern, public governance should address this by formulating solutions that foster the concurrent development of the primary sector in close coordination with other sectors.

Conclusion:

As Romania's mountain business continues its ascent across secondary, tertiary, and quaternary sectors, it becomes a testament to the adaptability and resilience of entrepreneurial endeavors in these awe-inspiring landscapes. Navigating the heights of economic development while preserving the intrinsic beauty of the mountains requires a strategic vision that harmonizes progress with environmental stewardship. In the tapestry of Romanian mountain business, each sector weaves a unique thread, contributing to the diverse and vibrant economic portrait painted against the backdrop of majestic peaks.

The study encompasses the following sectors:

- Industry, construction, and services, excluding insurance activities of companies (Ix);
- Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles (Ix1);
- Professional, scientific and technical activities; administrative and support activities (Ix2);
- Industry (excluding construction) (Ix3);
- Constructions (Ix4);

- Transport and storage (Ix5);
- Arts, entertainment, and recreation; other service activities (Ix6);
- Accommodation and food services (Ix7);
- Information and communication (Ix8);
- Education, human health, and social assistance (Ix9);
- Financial and insurance activities; real estate activities, excluding companies (Ix10).

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